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Benjamin Allen Sullivan

Unification

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1 Introduction

This publication is comprised of two equations which are derived and extrapolated from a book that I created in 2015/2016: Probability, Quantum Mechanics, and Probability-Quanta. The latter consists of various thought experiments and postulates. I have included scans from the original book in an effort to demonstrate my work and in the hopes of having the experiments conducted.

I do not have any formal education in physics and I realize that producing the publication without any academic background will see the work be dismissed or seen as suspect by many.

What I do possess is the ability to know when something is right.

2 Sullivan Unifying Constant

Title: Sullivan Unifying Constant

Author: Benjamin Allen Sullivan

Comments: Equation, 2 pages with 9 Figures

Subj-class: Physics

The Sullivan Unifying Constant is an equation that resolves the long-sought pursuit of understanding the unification of the known forces in the universe and how they interact with each other. This equation can be applied to or within any of the known sciences. The equation incorporates and demonstrates the interaction between forces known within “Classical Physics” and merges them with modern “Quantum Theory”.

1. Each individual component of the equation has been professionally pursued with vigour by various people, schools, and various scientific organizations. As mentioned, the equation incorporates and demonstrates the interaction between forces known within “Classical Physics” and merges them with modern “Quantum Theory”. It accomplishes this by incorporating the Spin Values (SV) of the Masses.
2. My equation resolves the long-sought pursuit of understanding the unification of the known forces in the universe and how they interact with each other. It does this by demonstrating the interchangeable nature of the known Force Carriers within the equation:
3. Figures:

Figure 1: Sullivan Unifying Constant Equation:

$$FC = T \frac{FCm1 \uparrow^{sv} FCm2 \downarrow^{sv}}{FCd^2}$$

Figure 2: $FC = \text{Any Force Carrier}$

FC

$FC = G$ for Gravity, EM for Electromagnetism, SF for Strong Force, WF for Weak Force.

Figure 3: Force Carriers

Figure 4: Sullivan Unifying Constant Equation Example Using Force of Gravity:

$$F = T \frac{SFm1 \uparrow^{sv} WFm2 \downarrow^{sv}}{EMd^2}$$

Figure 5: Equation Component #1 - Force of Gravity.

$$F$$

Figure 6: Equation Component #2 - Time (Constant).

$$T$$

Figure 7: Equation Component #3 - Strong Force (SF) - Mass 1 (m1) with indication of Spin Value (SV) Entangled or Otherwise.

$$SFm1 \uparrow^{sv}$$

Figure 8: Equation Component #4 - Weak Force (WF) - Mass 2 (m2) with indication of Spin Value (SV) Entangled or Otherwise.

$$WFm2 \downarrow^{sv}$$

Figure 9: Equation Component #5 - Electro Magnetism (EM) and Distance (d2).

$$EMd^2$$

4. Description: The Sullivan Unifying Constant demonstrates the interaction of the known forces within universe.
5. Examples of use: The Sullivan Unifying Constant provides enlightenment within all sciences. The equation offers a framework of understanding that allows for the creation of new technologies by progressing the field of science forward with new vigour derived from comprehension of the equation. Many of the implications (technological and otherwise) of the equation have yet to be discovered due to its newly formalized conception. It requires the contemplation of all with interest to achieve its maximum potential.

3 Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational Equation

Title: Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational Equation

Author: Benjamin Allen Sullivan

Comments: Equation, 2 pages with 6 Figures

Subj-class: Physics

The Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational Equation is related to Gravity within the field of Physics and all other affected Sciences. The equation is an alteration of Sir Isaac Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation. The equation merges and demonstrates the interaction between what is known as "Classical Physics" and modern "Quantum Theory".

1. As mentioned, the equation merges and demonstrates the interaction between what is known as "Classical Physics" and modern "Quantum Theory". It accomplishes this by incorporating the Spin Values (SV) of the Masses into the original equation. Individual components of the original Sir Isaac Newton equation have been professionally pursued with vigour by various people, schools, and various scientific organizations.
2. My equation resolves the long-sought pursuit of understanding the complete nature of Gravity.
3. Figures:

Figure 10: Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational Equation:

$$F = G \frac{M1 \uparrow^{sv} M2 \downarrow^{sv}}{D^2}$$

Figure 11: Equation Component #1 - Force of Gravity:

F

Figure 12: Equation Component #2 - Constant

G

Figure 13: Equation Component #3 - Mass 1 (M1) with indication of Spin Value (SV) Entangled or Otherwise.

M1 \uparrow^{sv}

Figure 14: Equation Component #4 - Mass 2 (M2) with indication of Spin Value (SV) Entangled or Otherwise.

M2 \downarrow^{sv}

Figure 15: Equation Component #5 – Distance (D^2)

$$D^2$$

4. Description: The Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational Equation demonstrates a comprehensive framework of Gravity.
5. Examples of use: The Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational Equation provides enlightenment within all sciences affected by Gravity. The equation offers a framework of understanding that allows for the creation of new technologies by progressing the field of science forward with new vigour derived from comprehension of the equation. Many of the implications (technological and otherwise) of the equation have yet to be discovered due to its newly formalized conception. It requires the contemplation of all with interest to achieve its maximum potential.

4 Probability, Quantum Mechanics, and Probability-Quanta
(Original Content and Thought Experiments)

FOREWARD

PROBABILITY, QUANTUM MECHANICS, AND PROBABILITY - GAUNTA
UNIFICATION WAS WRITTEN BY MYSELF OVER A PERIOD OF

ALTERED FORMULA

$$F = G \frac{M1 M2}{D^2}$$

NEWTONS LAW OF GRAVITY
CLASSIC

PROPOSED ALTERED FORMULA
(ENTANGLED PARTICLES / MASS SPIN)
PROPOSED

$$F = G \frac{\uparrow^{(sv)} M1 \downarrow^{(sv)} M2}{D^2}$$

SPIN VALUES FOR EACH MASS

PROPOSED EXPERIMENTS:

- VARIOUS POLARITIES WITH DIFFERENT WEIGHTS / MASS / SPIN(S)
- LOW KEVIN EXPERIMENT WITH THE SAME DATA
- VARIATIONS OF THE EXPERIMENT WITH DIFFERENT SPIN VALUES (sv) AND MASSES
- VARIOUS ENVIRONMENTS OF ELECTROMAGNETISM

$E = HF$
PLANCKS LAW

PROPOSED FORMULA:

$$\frac{I F (\sigma = \sigma^1 + \sigma^2, \text{ETC.}) = (1 + t) = E}{\lambda \text{ (XX FACTOR BASED ON WAVE AMPLITUDE)}}$$

OR:

$$\frac{\lambda^{(xx)} = I F^{(xx)}}{(1+t) = E} \therefore \lambda^{xx} = H$$

SO:
 (PROPOSED)

$$\lambda = \frac{H}{\text{CMB} \lambda \text{ (IN THIS CASE PEAK FREQUENCY)}}$$

OR:

$$E = \frac{HF}{\text{CMB}}$$

PROPOSED REVERSE EXPERIMENT-USE INTERFERENCE
PATTERN DATA "FIRST" AND REVERSING THE DATA
THROUGH TWO SLITS:

PROPOSED ENTANGLED PARTICLES ONLY EXPERIMENT

CONCEPTUAL VISUAL UNIFICATION AID

- 1. ELECTROMAGNETISM
- 2. GRAVITY
- 3. STRONG FORCE(S)
- 4. WEAK FORCE(S)
- 5. TIME
- 6. PROBABILITY

NOTE
 ALTHOUGH THE DIAGRAM IS POOR
 AT ILLUSTRATING IT, THE FORCES
 ARE IN EQUAL BALANCE AND
 POSSESS SYMMETRY.

BINARY EXPLANATION REGARDING DISTANCE OF ENTANGLED PARTICLES AND THEIR CORRESPONDING SPIN VALUES
 (SV)

$$F = G \frac{\overset{(SV)}{\uparrow} M1 \overset{(SV)}{\downarrow} M2}{(D)^2}$$

BINARY

DISTANCE APART (D²) ENTANGLED PARTICLES

PROBABILITY WAVE AMPLITUDE THEORY. I POSTULATE THAT THE CONVERGING POINTS ALTERNATE PARTICLE SPIN.

ENTANGLED PARTICLE SPIN VALUE (SV)
 DETERMINED BY WAVE AMPLITUDE \emptyset
 BINARY SYSTEM
 WAVE CONVERGING POINTS

\longleftrightarrow
 02

$$F = G \frac{\begin{matrix} \uparrow^{(sv)} M1 \\ \downarrow^{(sv)} M2 \end{matrix}}{02}$$

$$FC = T \frac{\overset{(ANY)}{\uparrow} FCm1 \overset{(ANY)}{\downarrow} FCm2}{FCd^2}$$

(TIME) CONSTANT

FC = ANY FORCE CAUSER

- GRAVITY
- ELECTROMAGNETISM
- STRONG FORCE
- WEAK FORCE

UNIFYING CONSTANT

PROPOSED UNIFYING THEORY
(GRAVITY EXAMPLE)

FORCE OF GRAVITY

$$F = T \frac{\overset{(SV)}{\uparrow} SFm1 \overset{(SV)}{\downarrow} WFm2}{EMd^2}$$

TIME CONSTANT

ELECTROMAGNETISM

$$F = T \frac{SFm1 \uparrow^{(sv)} WFm2 \downarrow^{(sv)}}{EMd^a}$$

$$F = MA$$

ENTANGLED POSITION

∅
PROBABILITY

$$F = G \frac{\uparrow M1^{(SV)} \downarrow M2^{(SV)}}{D^2}$$

1. WHAT EFFECT DOES THE DISTANCE BETWEEN THE PARTICLE GUN AND OBSERVATION SCREEN HAVE ON THE EXPERIMENT ???
- 2.

$$F = M A^{(SV)}$$

FORCE = MASS^(SV) X ACCELERATION WITH THE ADDITION OF THE SPIN VALUE (SV) ANNOTATED / MEASURED FOR THE ENTANGLED PARTICLE (S) ENTERING THE EXPERIMENT.

ENTANGLED PARTICLE GUN (SV)²

THE MAJORITY OF QM EXPERIMENTS HAVE BEEN CONDUCTED AT LOW TEMPERATURE CONDITIONS (WITH PROGRESSIVE EFFORT TOWARDS WARMER TEMPERATURES). I POSTULATE THAT WE ARE MISSING SIGNIFICANT ELEMENTS OF QM THEORY BY NOT CONDUCTING EXPERIMENTS AT HIGH TEMPERATURES. WITH THE REALIZATION THAT HIGH TEMPERATURES WITHIN QM EXPERIMENTS ARE DIFFICULT TO DETECT, EVERY EFFORT SHOULD BE MADE TO EXPERIMENT AT ALL TEMPERATURES.

HIGH-TEMP

MID

ULTRA-LOW

ALTERING SPIN VALUES (SV) OF ENTANGLED PARTICLES
FOR INFORMATION ENCODING AND TRANSMISSION

ALTERING THE SPIN VALUES IN THIS MANNER ALLOWS FOR THE ENCODING OF VARIOUS INFORMATION TYPES THAT MAY WORK BETTER IN ONE SPIN VALUE (SV) OPPOSED TO ANOTHER. THIS PROCESS WILL ALLOW FOR THE CHANGING OF ENTANGLED STATES SIMILAR TO THAT OF A TRADITIONAL "CRYPTO CHANGE". THIS WOULD BECOME RELEVANT WITH THE ADVANT OF ENTANGLED PARTICLE DETECTORS OR IF ENTANGLED "JAMMERS" WERE TO COME TO FRUITION.

ENTANGLED PARTICLE ENCODING AND SPIN VALUE (SV)

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INFORMATION
ENCODING
DEVICE

ENTANGLED PARTICLES ARE NOT LIMITED TO STRICTLY "UP OR DOWN" SPIN VALUES (SV). IN FACT, THEY ARE NOT LIMITED TO "THIRDS, $1/3$, $2/3$, $3/3$ " ETC. WHICH ARE COMMONLY USED WITHIN (TO DESCRIBE 1ST, 2ND, OR 3RD GENERATION) PARTICLES USED WITHIN PARTICLE ACCELERATORS AND OTHER EXPERIMENTS. AS YOU CAN SEE BELOW, I POSTULATE THAT EVERY PARTICLE (ENTANGLED OR OTHERWISE) IS CAPABLE OF POSSESSING A SPIN VALUE (SV) THAT IS OF AT LEAST OF 3 DIMENSIONS IN VALUE.

SV
SPIN VALUE

THE SPIN VALUE (SV) OF THESE PARTICLES CAN BE ALTERED IN THEIR NATURAL AND ENTANGLED STATES. THERE ARE VARIOUS METHODS FOR ENCODING (PAGES 8,9 OF THE ORIGINAL UNIFICATION PUBLICATION) AND VARIOUS METHODS FOR THE "TUNING" OF PARTICLES. ALL OF THESE METHODS CAN BE CONDUCTED DURING THE ENTANGLEMENT PROCESS OR THEY CAN BE "ADJUSTED" OR "TUNED" AFTER THE ENTANGLEMENT PROCESS. THIS ALLOWS FOR THE TRANSMISSION OF INFORMATION AT IT'S IDEAL WAVELENGTH/AMPLITUDE.

THE MASS ENTANGLEMENT OF PARTICLES IS PARTICULARLY USEFUL WHEN TRANSMITTING LARGE AMOUNTS OF INFORMATION AND WHEN TRANSMITTING AND RECEIVING INFORMATION OVER NUMEROUS DEVICES SUCH AS A RADIO NETWORK OR OTHER COMPLEX NETWORKS CONSISTING OF TWO OR MORE DEVICES. THESE MASS ENTANGLED PARTICLES CAN BE DISTRIBUTED AMONGST THE NETWORK TO FACILITATE EN MASS TRANSMISSION AND RECEIVING OF INFORMATION OR SPECIFIC TRANSMISSION BY ISOLATING PARTICLES ALICE'S OR BOB'S

MASS ENTANGLEMENT OF PARTICLES: ALPHABET METHOD

THE COMPLEXITY OF A QUANTUM COMMUNICATION SYSTEM MAY NECESSITATE THE REQUIREMENT MORE/NUMEROUS DIFFERENT TYPES OF ENTANGLED PARTICLES THAT SERVE SPECIFIC PURPOSES. FOR EXAMPLE, A RADIO NETWORK REQUIRES MASS ENTANGLEMENT OF "ALICE" AND "BOB" PARTICLES TO TRANSMIT AND RECEIVE ANALOG INFORMATION. THE SAME NETWORK REQUIRES A POWER TRANSMISSION CAPABILITY, AND IN THIS EXAMPLE REQUIRES THE ABILITY TRANSMIT AND RECEIVE DIGITAL INFORMATION. IN ORDER TO AVOID CONFOUNDING ENTANGLEMENT AND INFORMATION PASSAGE AND FOR DEVICE DESIGN, EACH SUBSET OF ENTANGLEMENT CAN BE ASSIGNED A PARTICULAR PURPOSE. IN THIS EXAMPLE, THE QUANTUM COMMUNICATION SYSTEM REQUIRES:

ALICE + BOB = ANALOG TRANSMISSION AND RECEIVING
CANDY + DONNIE = DIGITAL TRANSMISSION AND RECEIVING
EINSTEIN + FEYNMAN = POWER TRANSMISSION AND RECEIVING

I PROPOSE THE ALPHABET BELOW TO PROVIDE THE INITIAL 13 PAIRS OF ENTANGLED PARTICLES TO BE UTILIZED IN DEVICE/SYSTEM DESIGN AND EASE OF PROCESS COMPREHENSION. SUBSEQUENT ENTANGLED PARTICLES (FOR COMPLEX SYSTEMS) CAN UTILIZE AN ALPHANUMERIC SEQUENCE. FOR EXAMPLE: ALICE 01 + BOB 01, AND SO ON.

A ALICE

B BOB

C CANDY

D DONNIE

E EINSTEIN

F FEYNMAN

G GAILEO

H HEINRICH

I ISAAC

J JACK

K KATHRYN

L LISA

M MAX

N NEWTON

O OBI

P PAULI

Q QUEUE

R ROSALIND

S SAMANTHA

T TESLA

U URSULA

V VINCI

W WERNER

X XAVIER

Y YOUNG

Z ZED

ALPHANUMERIC SUBSETS

EXAMPLES:

ALICE 01
BOB 01
CANDY 08
DONNIE 08
URSULA 02
VINCI 02

ETC...

AN UNLIMITED AMOUNT OF ENTANGLED QUANTUM SUBSETS CAN BE UTILIZED IN THIS MANNER. QUANTUM IMPORTANT FOR COMPUTING AND OTHER QUANTUM FUNCTIONS.

QUANTUM INFORMATION CRYPTOGRAPHY BY ALTERING
THE SPIN VALUES (SV) OF ENTANGLED PARTICLES

QUANTUM INFORMATION IS ENCODED IN THE SAME MANNER DISCUSSED/DISPLAYED ON PAGES # 14, 15, 16, AND 17. QUANTUM ENCRYPTION OF THE INFORMATION TO BE SENT IS TO BE CONDUCTED AS ANOTHER SECURITY FEATURE OF THE QUANTUM INFORMATION TRANSMISSION PROCESS. THIS WOULD BE CONDUCTED IN THE CASE OF QUANTUM PARTICLE DETECTORS AND IN THE CASE OF THE UNIVERSAL USAGE OF PARTICULAR SPIN VALUES (SV) FOR THE TRANSMISSION OF CERTAIN TYPES OF INFORMATION; THE "TUNING" OF COMMONLY USED SPIN VALUES (SV). A QUANTUM COMPUTER WOULD PRODUCE AN ALGORITHM TO RANDOMIZE THE SPIN VALUE (SV) OF THE PARTICLES PRIOR TO TRANSMISSION. THIS WOULD RENDER DETECTORS USELESS/INABLE TO DECODE INFORMATION. FOR EXAMPLE, IF SPIN VALUE WAVELENGTH (SVW) THAT IS UTILIZED FOR DIGITAL INFORMATION IS COMMONLY TRANSMITTED AT A CERTAIN VALUE, THE QUANTUM ALGORITHM AND ENCRYPTION/ENCODING DEVICE WOULD RANDOMIZE THE SPIN VALUE (SV) PRIOR TO TRANSMISSION.

~ CREATION ~ :

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SPIN-VALUE (sv) PROBABILITY \emptyset

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APPLICATIONS

Acknowledgments

My acknowledgment and admiration to Sir Isaac Newton for the inspiration for my creation of the Sullivan-Newtonian Gravitational (SNG) Equation and for his contributions to our current understanding of our Universe. To Albert Einstein for the inspiration to discover the Sullivan Unifying Constant (SUC). To Richard Feynman for providing a method (Feynman Diagrams) to put my abstract thoughts and discoveries into coherent diagrams.

5 Conclusion

I welcome any correspondence on the content of the publication and I look forward to receiving your feedback.

Questions?

Postulates?

Problems?

Alterations?

Experimental Results?

6 Contact Information

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Thoughts